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Review Article

Preparation And Evaluation of Herbal Transdermal Patch for Management of Varicose Vein

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ABSTRACT

Varicose vein is condition that causes veins to bulge, swelling, twisting veins just below the skin's surface most often in the leg and feet. They are also offered in topical treatments that provide relief from associated symptoms such as pain, swelling, and inflammation, but can be inconvenient to frequent application. In this study we developed a novel herbal transdermal patch for varicose vein management using Curcuma longa (turmeric) and Centella asiatica extracts. Anti-inflammatory and wound healing properties are attributed to curcuma longa and collagen synthesis with antioxidant activity to Centella asiatica. The extracted plant materials were authenticated using great care before extraction using Soxhlet and maceration yields 37% w/w and 23.12% w/w respectively. Curcuminoids in Curcuma longa extracts and triterpenoids in Centella asiatica extracts were confirmed by thin layer chromatography. Since both extracts have poor lipid solubility, transdermal patches were selected to increase skin penetration. Three HPMC based patch formulations (F1, F2, F3) were developed and these were subsequently investigated for stability and in vivo in rat. F1 and F2 were loaded with HPMC 50, and with F3 a mixture of HPMC 50 and HPMC 15 was used. Pharmaceutical characterization of formulations was performed by organoleptic evaluation, pH determination, folding endurance, thickness, drug uniformity, drug release, in vitro antioxidant activity, and in vitro anti inflammation activity. According to all parameters, HPMC polymer combination in Batch F3 had optimal performance, holding and releasing both extracts in a controlled manner. Further stability studies also demonstrated the suitability of F3 formulation. Hence, the F3 Formula is completed for the herbal transdermal patch for varicose vein management.

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INTRODUCTION

Varicose veins are a condition where veins, typically in the legs, become permanently enlarged, twisted, and painful. This condition is often due to improperly functioning valves in the vein or weakness in the vein walls [1]. The causes of varicose veins are multifactorial and include increased intravenous pressure from prolonged standing, increased intra-abdominal pressure due to factors like tumors, pregnancy, obesity, or chronic constipation, as well as familial and congenital factors. Secondary vascularization from deep venous thrombosis or, less commonly, arteriovenous shunting, also contributes to their development [2]. Recent research highlights shear forces and inflammation as significant factors in venous disease etiology [3]. The fundamental pathophysiology involves valve reflux in the veins, where failed or incompetent valves cause blood to flow in reverse. This reverse flow increases pressure on the local venous system, causing affected veins to elongate and become tortuous. The specific cause of valvular dysfunction is generally thought to be the loss of elasticity in the vein walls, leading to valve leaflets that no longer fit together properly [4].

The prevalence of varicose veins varies by region, affecting approximately 2% to 73% of the global population [5]. It is estimated that about 33% of individuals aged 18 to 64 years are affected by varicose veins, which contributes significantly to healthcare costs. In Western countries, varicose veins are found in 10% to 15% of males and 20% to 25% of females [5].

Treatment options for varicose veins encompass conservative management, external laser treatment, injection sclerotherapy, endovenous interventions, and surgery. The choice of treatment is often guided by patient preference but also depends on factors such as symptom severity, cost, potential for complications, available medical resources, insurance coverage, physician

expertise, the presence of deep venous insufficiency, and the characteristics of the affected veins [6].

Transdermal patches represent an innovative and effective approach for delivering medications directly through the skin to treat varicose veins. This method offers several advantages over traditional oral or injectable medications, including improved patient compliance, controlled drug release, and reduced systemic side effects. Transdermal patches consist of a drug reservoir or matrix that contains the active pharmaceutical ingredient. When applied to the skin, the drug diffuses through the stratum corneum (the outermost layer of the skin) and enters the systemic circulation, or it can act locally to relieve symptoms associated with varicose veins.

In present study, we aimed to prepare and evaluate transdermal patch prepared by using *Curcuma longa* and *Centella asiatica* extracts for management of Varicose vein. *Curcuma longa* is well known anti-inflammatory herb while *Centella asiatica* is found to be effective in strengthening the blood capillary wall and also it promotes synthesis of collagen. In this study, we prepared *C. longa* and *C. asiatica* extracts by using ethanol as solvent. Transdermal patch was prepared by using polymers like HPMC 50, HPMC 15, plasticizers like polyethylene glycol, propylin glycol etc. The prepared formulation was evaluated by the physicochemical and biological parameters to make sure that formulation is successfully developed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

Based on extensive literature review and existing research work, *Centella asiatica* and *Curcuma longa* were selected for transdermal patch formulation. Dried powders of *Centella asiatica* and *Curcuma longa* were procured from authorized herbal drugs supplier. The procured plant materials were authenticated by the chemical

tests for presence of the desired phytochemicals before using for the formulation.

Chemicals

Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose 15, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose 50, Ethyl alcohol, Propylene glycol, Polyethylene Glycol 400, distilled water, 2,2 diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) procured from CDH Chemicals, New Delhi

Preliminary Phytochemical evaluation of plant material

Preliminary phytochemical investigation of procured dried powders of *asiatica* and *Curcuma longa* was done by conducting drug specific chemical tests. Following chemical tests were used:

Table 1. Chemical tests for identification of *Curcuma longa* and *Centella asiatica*

Sr. No	Name of Plant extract	Chemical test	Ref
1	<i>Curcuma longa</i> extract	Treatment with sulphuric acid gives red color	[7]
		Treatment with alkali solution gives red to violet color	
		.With acetic anhydride and concentrated sulphuric acid gives violet colour. Under UV light this colour is seen as an intense red fluorescence.	
		with borax solution gives .a green color	
		With boric acid gives reddish-brown color which, on addition of alkalies, changes to greenish-blue	
2	<i>Centella asiatica</i> extract	a) Foam test: - Shake the drug extract or dry powder vigorously with water b) Shinoda test: - To dry powder or extract, add 5 ml 95% ethanol/t-butyl alcohol, few drops conc.HCL and 0.5 g magnesium turnings. c) Salkowski reaction: - To 2 ml extract, add 2 ml chloroform and 2ml conc.H ₂ SO ₄ . Shake well. d) Borntrager's test :1gm of drug sample + 5-10 ml of dilute HCl + 10 min. boil on waterbath and filter + extract of filtrate with CCl ₄ or benzene + equal amount of ammonia solution to filtrate + shake → appearance of pink to red colour → indicate presence of anthraquinone moiety. e) Libermann Burchard test : Alcoholic extract of drug → evaporated → dry →extracted with CHCl ₃ + few drops of acetic anhydride + conc.salphuric acid (from the side wall of test tube) → appearance of violet ring → blue colour → presence of sterol group in drug.	

Extract Preparation

Preparation of *Curcuma longa* Extract

Ethanollic extract of *curcuma longa* was prepared by the Soxhlet extraction technique. 100 gms of *curcuma longa* powder was transferred in the Soxhlet apparatus and extracted for 6 hours with 350 ml of 95% ethanol at 40 – 50 °C temperature. After complete extraction, the extract was removed from the round bottom flask and concentrated at low temperature by evaporating excess of ethanol [8].

Preparation of *Centella asiatica* extract

Extraction of *Centella asiatica* was performed by maceration technique. In this method, 100 gm of *Centella asiatica* powder was added to 300 ml of 95% of ethanol in a 500 ml beaker. The mixture was kept for maceration with occasional stirring for 24 hrs at room temperature. After 24 hours, the mixture was filtered and extract was collected in conical flask. Again 300 ml of 95% of ethanol was added to the mark and kept for maceration for 24 hrs. The same process was repeated three times to ensure the complete extraction. All filtrates were collected together and concentrated to obtain percentage yield of extract [9]

Qualitative analysis of extracts by TLC

Thin layer chromatography of extracts of *curcuma longa*, *Centella asiatica* was performed using precoated Silica Gel G F254 to ensure the presence of desired phytochemicals in the extracts. Sample solutions for spot application on plate were

prepared by dissolving 1 mg of drug as well as reference standards in 5 ml methanol in separate test tubes. Purified Curcumin and asiaticosides used as reference standards. The mobile phases used for TLC analysis are as follows:

Table 2. Mobile phases for TLC analysis

Sr. No	Name of Extract	Mobile Phase
1	<i>Curcuma longa</i> ethanolic extract	Chloroform: methanol (97:3V/V) [10]
2	<i>Centella asiatica</i> alcoholic extract	Chloroform: glacial acetic acid: Glacial Acetic Acid: methanol: water. (6:3.2:1.2:8) [9]

Preparation of Transdermal patch formulation

Transdermal patch formulation was optimized by preparing three different batches F1, F2, F3 by

varying the quantities of ingredients (as shown in table 3).

Table 3. Batchwise preparation of herbal transdermal patch for optimization of formulation

Batch Code	Polymers	Chemicals	Excipients	Extracts
F1	HPMC 15 cps	3 gm of HPMC 15 + 40 ml of distilled water qs	Propylene Glycol 15%+ PEG 400 30%	<i>Curcuma longa</i> extract 5%, <i>Centella asiatica</i> extract 5 %
F2	HPMC 50 cps	3 gm of HPMC 50+ 40 ml of distilled water qs	Propylene Glycol 15%+ PEG 400 30%	<i>Curcuma longa</i> extract 5%, <i>Centella asiatica</i> extract 5 %
F3	HPMC 15 cps+HPMC 50 cps	1.5 gm of HPMC 15 +1.5 gm of HPMC 50 +40 ml of distilled water	Propylene Glycol 15%+ PEG 400 30%	<i>Curcuma longa</i> extract 5%, <i>Centella asiatica</i> extract 5 %

Transdermal patches with selected plant extracts were prepared by solvent casting method using Petri plates. Polymers HPMC 15, HPMC 50 and their combination were soaked in distilled water in separate beakers respectively for 24 hours at room temperature. After soaking, polymers were homogenized by using magnetic stirrer; the method used for transdermal patch formulation is as follows:

Initially polymers used in F1, F2 and F3 were kept for homogenization on magnetic stirrer for 1 hr at 100 rpm speed. Plant extracts of *curcuma longa* and *Centella asiatica* (500 mg each) were dissolved in 5 ml ethanol completely. Extracts were homogenized on magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes at 100 rpm. Extract mixture was added to

the polymer with continuous stirring on magnetic stirrer. Following addition of extracts, plasticizers PEG 400 and propylene glycol were added to the mixture and stirred well on magnetic stirrer for 1 hour. Each formulation was made up to 50 ml quantity using distilled water during homogenization process. After homogenization, the mixture was poured in petri plates in such a quantity that patch will become very thin [11].

Characterization of Formulation

Following parameters were evaluated to confirm the therapeutic efficacy of prepared formulation:

a) Organoleptic Evaluation

All the trial batches of transdermal patch formulations were tested for the color, odor, texture and appearance [12].

b) Determination of pH

Digital pH meter was used for the determination of the pH of F1, F2, F3 formulations of transdermal patch. For PH measurement, Transdermal patch was solublized in small amount of distilled water. PH detection rod was immersed in the solution and PH was recorded of each batch [12].

c) Thickness of formulation

The thickness of each formulation (F1, F2, and F3) was measured at five different locations (centre and four corners) using vernier caper and it was averaged to determine the mean thickness in mm [12].

d) Folding Endurance

Folding endurance of the patch formulation of each batch was determined by repeatedly folding one patch formulation at the same place till it broke [12].

e) Weight variation study

Ten samples of patch of each batch were weighed individually in a digital balance and the mean weights were calculated. It is useful to ensure that a film contains the proper number of excipients and API [12].

f)) Study of drug excipient compatibility by FTIR

FTIR spectroscopy was conducted to examine the interactions between the extracts and excipients. The analysis utilized a Shimadzu FTIR Spectrophotometer, with the extracts serving as controls for comparative assessment of interactions [12].

g) Drug Uniformity Test

A transdermal patch (2x2 cm) was dissolved in 100 ml of methanol and subjected to continuous shaking for 24 hours. The resulting solution was then sonicated for 15 minutes and filtered. The concentration of the drug in the filtered solution was determined spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 292 nm [12].

h) Invitro Drug Release studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted using a Franz diffusion cell system. The receptor compartment, with a 60 ml capacity, was filled with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer and maintained at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ to simulate normal human body temperature. A cellulose acetate membrane with a $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ pore size separated the donor and receptor compartments. Prepared transdermal patches were mounted on the membrane and sealed with aluminum foil. The receptor compartment solution was continuously stirred at 50 rpm using magnetic beads, following a method described by Simon et al. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined intervals, analyzed spectrophotometrically for drug content, and replaced with an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer. Care was taken during manual sampling to avoid introducing air bubbles into the receptor compartment [12].

g) Invitro drug efficacy studies

The therapeutic efficiency of prepared herbal transdermal patch was analyzed by using *invitro* assays of free radical scavenging activity by DPPH and invitro anti-inflammatory assay since free radicals and chronic inflammation are one of the well identified causative factors of psoriasis development.

i) Antioxidant activity by DPPH assay

Antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay, with gallic acid serving as the reference standard. A 1 mg/ml stock solution of gallic acid was prepared in ethanol and serially diluted to concentrations ranging from 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Similar serial dilutions (10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared for each batch of transdermal patches. A DPPH working solution was prepared by dissolving 10.83 mg of DPPH in ethanol and adjusting the final volume to 100 ml. Absorbance readings were taken at 520 nm, using the solvent (ethanol) as a blank and a DPPH solution without the transdermal patch formulation as a control [13].

Following formula used to calculate % free radical scavenging potential of prepared Transdermal patch: % Inhibition of free radicals = $\frac{\text{Absorbance of blank} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of Blank}}$

ii) **Invitro anti-inflammatory assay**

The anti-inflammatory potential of different emulgel formulations (F1-F3) was evaluated in vitro using a red blood cell membrane stabilization assay. Sheep red blood cells (50 μ l) were exposed to hypotonic solutions containing varying concentrations (12.5, 25, 50, and 100 ppm) of the transdermal patch formulations. A control group without the test formulations was also included. The isotonic solution consisted of 154 mM NaCl in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After a 10-minute incubation at room temperature, the samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 540 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. Diclofenac sodium (200 μ g/ml) was used as a reference standard. The % inhibition of red blood cell lysis was calculated by following formula [14]:

$$\% \text{ Red blood Cell membrane stability} = 100 \times [1 - \frac{\text{OD2} - \text{OD1}}{\text{OD3} - \text{OD1}}]$$

Here, OD1 represents the test sample in an isotonic solution, OD2 denotes the test sample in a hypotonic solution, and OD3 serves as the control sample in a hypotonic solution.

h) **Stability Study**

Stability testing was performed in alignment with the International Council for Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The finalized Transdermal patch formulation batch based on the above assessments underwent accelerated stability testing over a 3-month period under controlled conditions of $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ temperature and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity.

i) **Statistical analysis**

All values are expressed as Mean \pm SD. All data was analysed statistically by Single factor ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) by using graph pad prism Ver 5.1.0. The p value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) considered as statistically significant

Phytochemical evaluation of plant material outcomes

Selected plant materials *Centella asiatica* and *Curcuma longa* were examined by conducting phytochemicals specific chemical tests. Outcomes of the chemical tests are as follows (Table 4):

Table 4. Outcomes of preliminary phytochemical identification chemical tests

Sr. No	Name of Plant extract	Chemical test	Inference
1	<i>Curcuma longa</i> extract	Treatment with sulphuric acid gives red color	Curcuminoids present
		Treatment with alkali solution gives red to violet color	Curcuminoids present
		.With acetic anhydride and concentrated sulphuric acid gives violet colour. Under UV light this colour is seen as an intense red fluorescence.	Curcuminoids present
		with borax solution gives .a green color	Curcuminoids present
		With boric acid gives reddish-brown color which, on addition of alkalies, changes to greenish-blue	Curcuminoids present
2	<i>Centella asiatica</i> extract	a) Foam test: - Shake the drug extract or dry powder vigorously with water b) Shinoda test: - To dry powder or extract, add 5 ml 95% ethanol/t-butyl alcohol, few drops conc.HCL and 0.5 g magnesium turnings.	Saponins present Glycosidal flavanoids present, Steroids present,

	<p>c) Salkowski reaction: - To 2 ml extract, add 2 ml chloroform and 2ml conc.H₂SO₄. Shake well.</p> <p>d) Borntrager's test :1 gm of drug sample + 5-10 ml of dilute HCl + 10 min. boil on water bath and filter + extract of filtrate with CCl₄ or benzene + equal amount of ammonia solution to filtrate + shake → appearance of pink to red colour → indicate presence of anthraquinone moiety.</p> <p>e) Libermann burchard test : Alcoholic extract of drug → evaporated → dry →extracted with CHCl₃ + few drops of acetic anhydride + conc.salphuric acid (from the side wall of test tube) → appearance of violet ring → blue colour → presence of sterol group in drug.</p>	Glycosidal saponins present
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Hence, from above chemical tests, procured plant materials found authenticate and free from adulterants for further use in formulation

Extract preparation outcomes

Extracts of *Curcuma longa* was prepared by soxhlet extraction method by using 95% alcohol as a solvent. Ethanol selected as a solvent because curcuminoids are soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water. The percentage yield of the extract was found to be 37 %. *Centella asiatica* is rich source of saponin glycosides compounds which are soluble in solvents like ethanol hence; it was used

as solvent for extraction. The % yield of the *Centella* extract was found to be 23.12 %.

Qualitative analysis of extracts by TLC

Qualitative analysis of extracts for presence of desired phytochemicals was performed by Thin Layer Chromatography. In this method R_f value of reference standard is compared with the spots obtained from extract. For TLC analysis of *curcuma longa* and *Centella asiatica* extracts, curcumin and asiaticosides were used as reference standard The outcomes of the TLC analysis are as follows (Table 5)

Table 5. The outcomes of the TLC analysis

Sr. No	Name of Extract	Mobile Phase	Rf values obtained
1	<i>Curcuma longa</i> ethanolic extract	Chloroform: methanol (97:3V/V)	curcumin extract = 0.38 Std. Curcumin = 0.39
2	<i>Centella asiatica</i> alcoholic extract	Chloroform: glacial acetic acid: Glacial Acetic Acid: methanol: water. (6:3.2:1.2:8)	Centella extract = 0.34 Std. Asiaticoside = 0.35

The R_f values of curcumin and asiaticosides in extracts of *Curcuma longa* and *Centella asiatica* was found to be 0.38 and 0.34 respectively. These values found similar to the R_f values of respective reference standards. Hence the presence of phytoconstituents curcumin, and asiaticosides confirmed in extracts

4.4 Characterization outcomes of transdermal Formulation

The characterization of transdermal patch formulations is crucial for assessment of their physical, chemical, and functional properties, which affects their stability and efficacy. The

characterization involved analyzing parameters like organoleptic evaluation, pH determination, thickness, folding endurance, moisture content determination, drug content uniformity test, invitro drug release study and invitro efficacy studies like antioxidant activity and anti-inflammatory activity to ensure the formulation is appropriate for use. The outcomes of the characterization of transdermal patch formulation are as follows:

a) Organoleptic parameters evaluation

All the trial batches of Transdermal patch formulations were tested for the color, odor,

texture and appearance. The outcomes of the test are discussed in the table as follows (Table 6):

Table 6. The outcomes of the organoleptic test

Sr. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3
1	Color	Yellowish	Yellowish	Yellowish
2	Odor	Characteristic	Characteristic	pleasant
3	Texture	Slightly rough	smooth	Smooth
4	Appearance	solid	solid	solid

b) Determination of pH

Determination of pH of the transdermal patch is a crucial parameter to investigate the suitability of patch with the skin pH. The outcomes of test are as follows:

Table 7. Outcomes of pH determination

Parameters	F1	F2	F3
pH	6 ± 0.10	6.2±0.66	6.5±0.12

Data expressed in terms of mean±SD. The data found to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$

Topical formulations pH should be compatible with human skin unless it causes skin irritation and reduces patient acceptability. Ideal pH of human skin is 6.5 – 6.8. Hence, the pH of the formulation batches F3 found to be in the range of 6.6 – 6.8 compatible with the human skin.

c) Thickness of formulation

Evaluation of thickness of transdermal patch is an important aspect as it directly affects the drug release and efficacy of the transdermal patch. The thickness of each formulation (F1, F2, and F3) was measured at five different locations (centre and four corners) using vernier caliper and it was averaged to determine the mean thickness in mm. The outcomes of these evaluation parameters are as follows:

Table 8. Outcomes of thickness determination of herbal transdermal patches

Sr. No	Thickness of F1	Thickness of F2	Thickness of F3
1	0.34±0.02	0.31±0.42	0.20±0.54
2	0.34±0.23	0.33±0.25	0.20±0.65
3	0.35±0.33	0.31±0.44	0.20±0.78

Data expressed in terms of mean±SD. The data found to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$

Out of F1, F2, F3 batch formulation, F3 shown appropriate thickness as compared to the remaining two batches. Hence from this study, it is conclude that F3 batch thickness is appropriate as per the formulation requirement.

d) Folding Endurance

Folding endurance of the patch formulation indicates flexibility of the patch. The patch of each batch was determined by repeatedly folding one patch formulation at the same place till it broke. The outcomes of folding endurance are as follows (Table 9):

Table 9. The outcomes of folding endurance test of Herbal transdermal patch

Sr. No	Folding endurance of F1	Folding endurance of F2	Folding endurance of F3
1	101	56	117
2	100	56	115
3	100	59	110

In terms of mean ±SD, folding endurance of batch F1, F2 and F3 found to be 100.3 ± 4.96 , 57 ± 2.96 and 114 ± 4.70 respectively. Among all these batches, F3 batch has shown good folding endurance.

e) Weight variation study

five samples of patch 2×2 of each batch were weighed individually in a digital balance and the mean weights were calculated. It is useful to ensure that a film contains the proper number of excipients and API. The outcomes of the study are as follows:

Table 10. Weight variation study outcomes of herbal transdermal patches

Sr. No	Weight of F1 (mg)	Weight of F2 (mg)	Weight of F3 (mg)
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1	0.124	0.123	0.124
2	0.125	0.124	0.121
3	0.123	0.122	0.121
4	0.126	0.124	0.122
5	0.124	0.121	0.124

No significant weight variation was found in all three batches. Hence all three batches passed the test

f) Study of drug excipient compatibility by FTIR

FTIR spectroscopy was conducted to examine the interactions between the extracts and excipients. The analysis utilized a Shimadzu FTIR Spectrophotometer, with the extracts serving as controls for comparative assessment of interactions.

Figure 1 FTIR spectra of Curcumin extract

Figure 2 FTIR spectra of F3 transdermal patch

Table 11. FTIR analysis of curcuma extract and transdermal patch F3

Sr. No	Funcitnal groups of curcumin	Frequency in cm-1 of curcumin extract	Frequency in cm-1 of F3
1	C=O caobonyl [satureted aliphatic]	1743.72	1743.72
2	CH aliphatic sterchning	2978.22	2985.94
3	CH aromatic srechning	3364.00	-
4	C=C benzene ring	1612.56	1651.14
5	Hydroxy group	3526.03	3541.46
6	Aldehede stechning	2600.00	2947.36
7	C and H bond stechning	2978.22	2947.36

Figure 3 FTIR spectra of Centella extract

Figure 4 FTIR spectra of F3 transdermal patch

Table 12. FTIR analysis of Centella extract and transdermal patch F3

Sr. No	Functional groups of Centella	Frequency in cm-1 of Centella extract	Frequency in cm-1 of F3
1	CH aromatic stretching	2955.07	2985.00
3	C=O carbonyl [saturated aliphatic]	1705.15	1743.72
4	C=C benzene ring	1651.14	1651.14
5	Hydroxy group	3570.60	3541.48
6	O-H bending	1165.05	1165.00

From above study, it is observed that, no significant drug excipients interactions present in F3 formulation.

g) Drug Uniformity Test

Drug uniformity test is important parameter to ensure drug is uniformly blended with polymer so that dosing will be accurate. The outcomes of drug uniformity test are as follows (Table 13):

Table 13. Outcomes of drug uniformity test of herbal transdermal formulations

Sr. No	% drug content F1	% drug content F2	% drug content F3
1	98.23	96.45	99.01
2	95.11	97.94	98.21
3	97.23	98.17	99.87

Data expressed in terms of mean \pm SD. The data found to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$ in terms of mean \pm SD, The % drug release of batch F1, F2 and F3 was found to be 96.85%, 97.52% and 99.03 % respectively. Thus based on above outcomes, it is observed that, drug uniformity is more in F3 formulation as compared to other formulations.

h) In vitro Drug Release studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted using a Franz diffusion cell system. The receptor

compartment, with a 60 ml capacity, was filled with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer and maintained at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ to simulate normal human body temperature. A cellulose acetate membrane with a $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ pore size separated the donor and receptor compartments. Prepared transdermal patches were mounted on the membrane and sealed with aluminum foil. The receptor compartment solution was continuously stirred at 50 rpm using magnetic beads, following a method described by Simon et al. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined intervals, analyzed spectrophotometrically for drug content, and replaced with an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer. The UV wavelength of curcumin and Asiaticosides found to be 430 and 210 nm respectively. % drug release from transdermal patch was determined by analyzing the samples withdrawn at time intervals of 0, 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 minutes at 430 and 210 nm respectively to find out presence of phytoconstituents in each sample. The % drug release of phytoconstituents like curcumin and asiaticosides from F1, F2 and F3 are as follows (Table 14):

Table 14 outcomes of % drug release of phytoconstituents curcumin and asiaticosides from F1, F2 and F3

Formulation		% drug release at 0 min	% drug release at 50 min	% drug release at 100 min	% drug release at 150 min	% drug release at 200 min	% drug release at 250 min
F1	Curcumin	0	2.0 \pm 0.12	7.23 \pm 0.22	13.21 \pm 1.24	26.23 \pm 0.67	40.19 \pm 0.33
	Asiaticosides	0	13.10 \pm 0.11	26.34 \pm 1.03	38.22 \pm 1.07	47.89 \pm 1.23	58.56 \pm 0.32
F2	Curcumin	0	6.0 \pm 0.42	14.1 \pm 0.10	34.2 \pm 0.56	42.2 \pm 0.66	47.18 \pm 0.43
	Asiaticosides	0	11.34 \pm 0.11	23.23 \pm 1.03	36.20 \pm 1.07	49.65 \pm 1.23	54.30 \pm 0.32
F3	Curcumin	0	16.89 \pm	37.11 \pm	47.5 \pm	56.23 \pm	62.55 \pm

			0.10	0.43	0.29	0.22	0.76
	Asiaticosides	0	19.34± 0.11	27.23± 1.03	40.20± 1.07	55.65± 1.23	69,12± 0.32

Data expressed in terms of mean±SD. The data found to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$

All three batches of transdermal patch (F1, F2, F3) shown significant amount of drug release. Among all three batches, the better drug release was observed in F3 formulation.

i) Invitro drug efficacy studies

The therapeutic efficiency of prepared herbal transdermal patch was analyzed by using *invitro*

assays of free radical scavenging activity by DPPH and invitro anti-inflammatory assay since free radicals and chronic inflammation are one of the well identified causative factors for varicose vein.

a) Antioxidant activity by DPPH assay

The outcomes of invitro anti-oxidant activity are as follows:

Table 15. Invitro antioxidant study outcomes

Sr. No	Name of Sample	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Inhibition
1	Ascorbic acid (Reference standard)	10	84.66±0.11
		20	86.80±0.02
		30	88.05±0.14
		40	91.30±0.23
		50	94.00±0.43
2.	batch F1	10	60.75±0.23
		20	63.32±0.11
		30	65.90±0.34
		40	70.82±0.22
		50	71.77±0.56
	batch F2	10	49.70±0.44
		20	52.74±0.56
		30	56.21±0.43
		40	61.23±0.98
		50	62.21±0.67
	batch F3	10	64.48±0.33
		20	67.95±0.76
		30	73.09±0.55
		40	78.02±0.87
		50	87.62±0.30

Data expressed in terms of mean±SD. The data found to be statistically significant with $p < 0.05$

Figure.5 Anti-oxidant activity curve of standard drug Gallic acid

Figure.6 Anti-oxidant activity curve of F1 transdermal patch formulation

Figure.7 Anti-oxidant activity curve of F2 transdermal patch formulation

Figure.8 Anti-oxidant activity curve of F3 transdermal patch formulation

In this study, all formulations F1, F2, F3 have shown free radical scavenging activity however, F3 batch shown significantly more anti-oxidant activity than F1 and F2. This may be due to the more drug release through combined polymer matrix.

b) *In vitro* anti-inflammatory assay

Chronic inflammation is one of the leading cause of development of varicose veins. Hence, it was crucial to analyze formulation for its therapeutic efficacy as an anti-inflammatory agent. The outcomes of this study are as follows:

Table 16. Anti-inflammatory activity outcomes of herbal transdermal patches

Sr. No	Name of Sample	Conc. (µg/ml)	% Inhibition
1	F1	12.5	37.29±0.02
		25	40.30 ±0.04
		50	37.88±0.23
		100	40.84±0.11
2	F2	12.5	34.45±0.23
		25	43.40 ±0.44
		50	46.91±0.20
		100	51.13±0.75
3	F3	12.5	40.73±0.34
		25	43.20±0.55
		50	50.90±0.32
		100	61.03±0.16

Data expressed in terms of mean±SD. The data found to be statistically significant with p < 0.05

In this study, all three batches of transdermal patch shown significant anti-inflammatory activity. However, batch F3 shown significantly more anti-inflammatory activity as compared to F2 and F3.

h) Stability Study

Stability studies were conducted in Environmental test chamber to assess stability of formulation with respect to their physical appearance, after storing them at 45⁰c/75% RH for 3 months. The formulation found to be stable after 3 months period. No changes in physical appearance observed.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the herbal transdermal patch formulation F3 showcased potential as effective therapeutic agent for management of varicose vein. Ayurvedic herbs *Centella asiatica* and *Curcuma longa* whose chief active constituents are curcumin and asiaticosides, are poorly lipid soluble in their pure form. Hence incorporating them in transdermal patch can enhance their therapeutic effect by enhancing skin permeation. In this way, developed herbal transdermal patch can be an effective strategy for varicose veins treatment. However, these outcomes needs to be confirmed by *invivo* studies before commercialization.

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